

HORIZON 2020 - Coordination and Support Action

Grant Agreement No: 101003766

**EU-PolarNet 2 - Co-ordinating and Co-designing the
European Polar Research Area**

Deliverable No. 3.6

**Summary report of outcomes of the second call
for services**

Submission of Deliverable

Document information	
Work Package	WP 3 Research Prioritisation
Deliverable No	D3.6
Deliverable title	Summary report of outcomes of the second call for services
Version	V2
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public <input type="checkbox"/> PP - Restricted to programme partners <input type="checkbox"/> RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium <input type="checkbox"/> CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium
Lead Beneficiary	AWI (partner 1)
Contributors	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI, <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – MICINN, <input type="checkbox"/> 3 – UOULU, <input type="checkbox"/> 4 – ISP-CNR, <input type="checkbox"/> 5 – RCN, <input type="checkbox"/> 6 – EPB, <input type="checkbox"/> 7 - NWO, <input type="checkbox"/> 8 – DAFSHE, <input type="checkbox"/> 9 - CNRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – UoS-CPS, <input type="checkbox"/> 11 – BAI, <input type="checkbox"/> 12 – UNIVIE, <input type="checkbox"/> 13 –IG-TUT, <input type="checkbox"/> 14 – WOC Europe, <input type="checkbox"/> 15 – BELSPO, <input type="checkbox"/> 16 – AMAP, <input type="checkbox"/> 17 – IGOT UL, <input type="checkbox"/> 18 - SPRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 19 – UKRI-BAS, <input type="checkbox"/> 20 – ITU, <input type="checkbox"/> 21 – USB, <input type="checkbox"/> 22 – RANNIS, <input type="checkbox"/> 23 – FAMRI, <input type="checkbox"/> 24 – ICR, <input type="checkbox"/> 25 – SPI
Coordinating author	Anneli Strobel, Nicole Biebow
Contributing authors	
Due date	31.05.2023
Delivery date	19.04.2023

Document history	
Creation Date	31.01.2023
Revision	V2
Revision Date	2023
Author	AWI
Status	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP lead approved <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Coordinator approved <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Executive Board approved
Status date	19.04.2023

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003766

TABLE OF CONTENTS

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY	4
1 Introduction	5
2 Conditions and scope of the 2nd Call for Services	6
2.1 Call conditions	6
2.2 Call documentation	6
2.2.1 Updates from 1 st Call for services.....	6
2.3 Eligibility criteria	6
2.4 Eligibility criteria	7
2.5 Evaluation and selection procedure	7
2.6 Call advertisement	9
3 Results of the 2nd Call for Services	10
3.1 Submitted offers	10
3.2 Evaluation and selection of offers	11
3.2.1 Evaluation procedure	11
3.2.2 Evaluation outcome.....	11
4 Outlook	12
5 Annexes	13
5.1 Evaluation template	13
5.2 Standard Service Contract.....	17

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

One of the objectives of EU-PolarNet 2 is to prioritise and specify the key societally relevant Polar research themes, which have been defined in the [European Polar Research Programme \(EPRP\)](#), the EU-PolarNet White Papers and in European Polar strategies.

With launching calls for services, EU-PolarNet 2 seeks support from the European Polar Community to further develop the research themes identified in the EPRP into achievable research projects that could be funded on a national, European or international level.

For this purpose, EU-PolarNet 2 opened three Calls for Services for all six research needs of the European Polar Research Programme:

- 1) Better understanding of climate change in the Polar Regions and its links to lower latitudes
- 2) Informed weather and climate action
- 3) Resilient socio-ecological systems
- 4) Prospering communities in the Arctic
- 5) Challenges and Opportunities for Polar Operations
- 6) Inclusive creation, access and usage of know ledge

This deliverable reports on the second call for services, which asked to formulate achievable research activities related to one of the key questions/sub-topics of following two Research Needs of the EPRP:

- Resilient socio-ecological systems
- Challenges and Opportunities for Polar Operations

1 Introduction

One of the objectives of EU-PolarNet 2 is to prioritise and specify the key societally relevant Polar research themes, which have been defined in the [European Polar Research Programme \(EPRP\)](#), the EU-PolarNet White Papers and in European Polar strategies.

With launching calls for services, EU-PolarNet 2 seeks support from the European Polar Community to further develop the research themes identified in the EPRP into achievable research projects that could be funded on a national, European or international level.

For this purpose, EU-PolarNet 2 opened three consecutive Calls for Services, the third Call for Services closed on 20th of December 2022. The calls asked to formulate achievable research activities for two of the six research needs of the European Polar Research Programme, each:

- 1) Better understanding of climate change in the Polar Regions and its links to lower latitudes
- 2) Informed weather and climate action
- 3) Resilient socio-ecological systems (Call 2)
- 4) Prospering communities in the Arctic (Call 1)
- 5) Challenges and Opportunities for Polar Operations (Call 2)
- 6) Inclusive creation, access and usage of knowledge (Call 1)

For each granted service contract, EU-PolarNet 2 offered up to 15.000 € financial support to European (early career) researchers and/or stake- and rightsholders as seed money to cultivate ideas for future research projects of wide European interest and high societal relevance. The service contract can be used to organise international workshops and meetings, e.g. for preparing White Papers or joint research proposals, to invite e.g. stake- and rightsholders or early career researchers, to perform pre-studies or for any other method leading to the development of ideas/proposals for priority research.

The [second Call for Services](#) was opened on 15 March 2022 and the deadline for offers was 20 May 2022. EU-PolarNet 2 invited European (early career) researchers and/or stake- and rightsholders to submit an offer related to one of the key questions/sub-topics of following two Research Needs of the [European Polar Research Programme](#):

- 1) Resilient socio-ecological systems
- 2) Challenges and Opportunities for Polar Operations

This call offered financial support of up to 15.000 € to cover expenses necessary for successfully implementing the proposed activities, with a maximum budget of 40.000 €.

2 Conditions and scope of the 2nd Call for Services

2.1 Call conditions

- The [second EU-PolarNet 2](#) Call for Services was open from **15 March 2022** to **20 May 2022**, 14:00 CET.
- It was specified in the application guidelines that the duration of a service contract is 12 months maximum as of the signature of the contract. Applicants could provide offers for a maximum budget of 15.000€. The total budget of the second Call for Services was 40.000€.
- Applicants were asked to send their offers electronically (in pdf format, unprotected, 5 MB max.) to the info@eu-polarnet.eu email address.
- The implementation of the service contract will require tools and/or approaches to be effective and achieve its objectives. For example, site visits and conferences, workshops, desk studies, setting up networks, web interfaces or fora, platforms, measures to promote stakeholders' involvement, are all tools and approaches through which the service objectives can be achieved.
- A principal obligation of a successful service provider is the submission of a report on the work performed to EU-PolarNet 2 within one month after the conclusion of the service contract.

2.2 Call documentation

2.2.1 Updates from 1st Call for services

After evaluating the applications for the 1st EU-PolarNet 2 Service Contracts and negotiating the funded Service Contracts, we have added the following updates to the call documentation for the following Service Calls:

- a) We asked the applicants to use only the [CV template](#) that we provide on the EU-PolarNet 2 website.
- b) We added the following essential condition to the application guidelines:
Successful offers will be contracted by the EU-PolarNet 2 coordinator (Alfred-Wegener Institute (AWI)) to provide their services to EU-PolarNet 2. By submitting an offer, applicants agree to the [standard service contract](#) of the AWI (see Appendix). The terms of the contract are not negotiable.
- c) We provided a reporting template (Annex) for the successful, granted Service Providers.

2.3 Eligibility criteria

The second EU-PolarNet 2 Call for Services asked to formulate achievable research activities or projects related to one of the key questions/sub-topics of **two of the Research Needs of the EPRP**:

1) RESILIENT SOCIO-ECOLOGICAL SYSTEMS

This includes the following key questions:

- Understanding key issues of polar ecosystem structure, functioning, and change.

- Designing a healthy socio-ecological system.
- Expanding observation of socio-ecological systems.
- Ecosystem-based management, governance and transformative solutions towards a sustainable future.

2) CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR POLAR OPERATIONS

This includes the following key questions:

- Understanding the impacts of changing environmental conditions and operations on risk and vulnerability.
- Minimising the environmental impacts of polar operations.
- Understanding and promoting the concept of social license for polar operations.

2.4 Eligibility criteria

Service providers had to meet the following eligibility criteria:

1. **Type:** the call for services is open to European (early career) researchers and/or stake- and rightsholders, hereafter named service providers.
2. **Affiliation:** The service providers need to be based in a European Member State or in a country that is associated to the EU framework programme¹.
3. **Partnership:** Offers must involve at least two partners from two different countries².
4. **Dissemination:** Service providers are obliged to disseminate the knowledge they have acquired. The proposal must include a dissemination plan to be eligible for funding. Service providers must agree to comply with the [EU's General Data Protection Regulation](#).

2.5 Evaluation and selection procedure

The evaluation procedure and selection of offers were organised by the EU-PolarNet 2 consortium and performed by its Polar Expert Group (PEG). The PEG is the EU-PolarNet 2 Expert Forum for implementing European Polar research internationally, by specifying overarching priorities, research needs and specific actions. The PEG is comprised of internationally recognised experts in all kinds of Polar Research, including representatives from the EU Polar Cluster projects, Indigenous researchers and researchers from business, NGOs or other stakeholders performing research in the Polar Regions. More information about the PEG can be found [here](#).

The general evaluation criteria that were taken into consideration by the experts were the following:

¹ Proponents from Associated Countries can participate under the same conditions as proponents from the Member States. The following countries have indicated that they will associate to Horizon Europe: Iceland, Norway, Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, Turkey, Israel, Moldova, Switzerland, Faroe Islands, Ukraine, Tunisia, Georgia, Armenia; UK.

² EU-PolarNet 2 beneficiaries may apply for the service contracts, but the majority of the participants in the offer must not be EU-PolarNet 2 beneficiaries.

a. Eligibility

For all submitted offers, the following eligibility criteria were examined:

- The submission file is complete.
- The submission file was submitted in electronic format (in pdf).
- The submission file was submitted no later than 20 May 2022 - 14h00 CET.
- **Research theme:** offers must be related **one of the key questions** described in section 3.
- **International cooperation:** offers must involve at least two partners from two different countries.
- **Dissemination Plan:** Service providers are obliged to disseminate the knowledge they have acquired during the service contract.
- The duration of the funding of the service is maximum **12 months**.
- The applications must comply with the budget requirements.
- The offer is not an ongoing research project.

Only the offers that met **ALL** these criteria were evaluated.

b. Compliance with the content of the present call

- The offer is designed to contribute to the research prioritisation process of EU-PolarNet 2
- The offer does not overlap with activities foreseen in EU-PolarNet 2

c. Quality of the offer

- Is the focus of the offer clearly defined with regard to the EU-PolarNet 2 project?
- Are the objectives of the offer well thought out and clearly stated?
- Is the stake- and rightsholder community included in a respectful way (composition, type of involvement...)?
- Is the implementation of the service coherent with the respect to its objectives: management, approaches and tools.
- Is the proposed work expected to provide added value to the EU-PolarNet 2 project?
- Is the expected service impact well assessed, measured, feasible and realistic?
- Are dissemination activities addressing the general public/stakeholders/research community planned?

d. Tasks, budget, timing

- Relevance of tasks and relevance of their distribution in the service network with respect to the objectives of the offer.
- The proposed tasks are appropriate for the given time frame.

- Cost-efficient use of resources. Since EU-PolarNet 2 is offering service contracts the criteria of best value for money and provisions of conflict of interest³ apply.

2.6 Call advertisement

The 2nd Service Call was advertised through the following channels:

- Banner on EU-PolarNet 2 [website](#)
- Quarterly EU-PolarNet 2 newsletter in [March 2022](#)
- EU-PolarNet 2 Facebook page
 - <https://www.facebook.com/groups/1442027029433733/permalink/2974272289542525/>
 - <https://www.facebook.com/groups/1442027029433733/permalink/3007412549561832/>
- EU-PolarNet 2 Twitter channel (@EUPolarNet). Five dedicated posts and reminders, up to 1240 impressions per post.
- EU Polar Cluster website
- EU Polar Cluster Twitter channel (e.g. <https://twitter.com/EUPolarCluster/status/1506572135648702466?s=20&t=bMcgP1gjz7eFW5qBHULw2w>)
- Catalyst platform
- [Posts](#) at EU-PolarNet 2 LinkedIn group

³ EU-PolarNet 2 must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the service contract is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest.

3 Results of the 2nd Call for Services

3.1 Submitted offers

Four offers were submitted to the 2nd EU-PolarNet 2 Call for Services (Table 1). All offers fulfilled the eligibility criterion on international collaboration. Yet, none of the applications complied with the content of the call to design the offer for a contribution to research prioritisation process of EU-PolarNet 2.

Two of the offers were submitted for the research need “Resilient socio-ecological systems”, one for the research need “Inclusive creation, access and usage of knowledge”, and one did not specify to which research need it was contributing to.

Table 1: Overview of submitted offers to 2nd EU-PolarNet 2 Call for Services

Proposal No.	Research Need	Focus	Coordinator Country
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.1 (Understanding key issues of polar ecosystem structure, functioning, and change) 3.3 (Expanding observation of socio-ecological systems) 5.2 (Minimising the environmental impacts of polar operations) 	Arctic lakes, local communities, ice and vegetation phenology, environmental and climate change	Austria
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.3 (Expanding observation of socio-ecological systems) 3.4 (Ecosystem-based management, governance and transformative solutions toward a sustainable future) 6.2 (Co-production of knowledge as a benefit to societal stakeholders) 	Traditional knowledge, culture, web platform, need for improvement in Arctic policies in Finland and EU	Portugal
3	Not specified	Fish skin, socio-economy, craft practices, Arctic indigenous peoples	United Kingdom
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4.7 (Cultural vitality for prosperity in the Arctic) 6 (Inclusive creation, access and usage of knowledge) 	Queer identity, Polar sciences, awareness, call for action to policymaking	Iceland

Overall, most of the applicants came from Austria (4), followed by Germany (2), Iceland (2), and one each from Finland, Norway, Portugal, Spain, Sweden and the United Kingdom.

Five of the applicants who were part of the submitted offers were Early Career Researchers, all of them female. One of them acted as PI of a submitted offer.

Figure 1: Diagram showing the nationality of all applicants to the 2nd Call for Services, as an indicator for international collaboration (9 countries for 4 offers).

3.2 Evaluation and selection of offers

3.2.1 Evaluation procedure

The evaluation process of the offers submitted to the EU-PolarNet 2 Service Calls was as follows:

- 1) PART I: Evaluation by the EU-PolarNet 2 Executive Board to verify if the offers comply with the scope of the call
- 2) PART II: Evaluation by independent, external experts

The Executive Board and the external reviewers were asked to comment and rate each of the offers following the evaluation criteria and questions of the evaluation template in ANNEX 5.1.

The idea of this two-step evaluation process was that only offers which fully complied with the scope of the call (PART I of the evaluation template) were considered as eligible for funding were forwarded to external expert evaluation (PART II).

3.2.2 Evaluation outcome

During the PART I evaluation, the Executive Board noted that none of the submitted offers complied with the scope of the call. The reasons for rejecting the offers were:

- The offers did not make clear how the planned work will lead to new future research ideas that support EU-PolarNet 2 in its research prioritisation task.

- The call for services is not intended to support ongoing research or projects, but to support the development of new ideas to further develop the research themes identified in the EPRP into achievable research projects.

The EU-PolarNet 2 Executive Board held a virtual meeting and concluded that none of offers were expected to provide an added value to the EU-PolarNet 2 project and should therefore not be included in PART II of the evaluation process.

The offers which were not selected for funding received a rejection letter an explanation that the offers could not make sufficiently clear which part of the planned work will lead to new future research ideas and that ongoing research is not supported by EU-PolarNet 2.

4 Outlook

The third Call for Services was opened on 20 September 2022 and deadline for offers was 20 December 2022. EU-PolarNet 2 invited European (early career) researchers and/or stake- and rightsholders to submit an offer related to one of the key questions/sub-topics of following two Research Needs of the EPRP:

- Better understanding of climate change in the Polar Regions and its links to lower latitudes
- Informed weather and climate action

The evaluation of the submitted offers for the third and last EU-PolarNet 2 Service Call took place in spring 2023 and will be specified in D3.9 *Summary report of outcomes of the third call for services*.

5 Annexes

5.1 Evaluation template

Call for Services 2022 (03)

OFFER EVALUATION TEMPLATE

OFFER ID	
Offer Acronym	Click here to enter text.
Offer Title	Click here to enter text.
Research Theme	<input type="checkbox"/> RESILIENT SOCI-ECOLOGICAL SYSTEMS <input type="checkbox"/> CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR POLAR OPERATIONS

PART I: EXECUTIVE BOARD EVALUATION

Compliance with the scope of the present call

Is the offer rightly focused on contributing to the research prioritisation process of EU-PolarNet 2?	Choose: Yes - No
<i>The project has been implemented to ... identify and prioritise polar research themes of high societal relevance... which have been defined in the <u>European Polar Research Programme (EPRP)</u>, the EU-PolarNet White Papers and in European Polar strategies.</i>	
Comments (motivate):	
Is the offer in line with the general objectives of the call for services?	Choose: Yes - No
<i>With launching calls for services, EU-PolarNet 2 seeks support from the European Polar Community to further develop research ideas into achievable research projects that could be funded on a national, European or international level. The research themes shall be based on the research needs defined in the EPRP and shall contribute to specific key questions. The service contract can be used to organise international workshops and meetings, e.g. for preparing White Papers or joint research proposals, to invite e.g. stake- and rightholders or early career researchers, to perform pre-studies or for any other method leading to the expected outcome.</i>	
Comments (motivate):	
Does the offer answer to the research priorities of the Call (cfr. section 3 of the information guidelines)?	Choose: Yes - No
<p><i>PROSPERING COMMUNITIES IN THE ARCTIC</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>An infrastructure plan in support of sustainable community development.</i> • <i>National and sub-national governance challenges in the Arctic Regions.</i> • <i>Economic innovations for sustainable development of Arctic communities.</i> • <i>Education as a tool to expand the capacity of Arctic residents to respond to changes.</i> • <i>Learning from the past for a socio-economically balanced and gender-equal development of the Polar Regions.</i> • <i>The demography of the future Arctic population.</i> • <i>Cultural vitality for prosperity in the Arctic.</i> <p><i>INCLUSIVE CREATION, ACCESS AND USAGE OF KNOWLEDGE</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Developing new technologies and improved capacities in observation, modelling, and research in the Polar regions.</i> • <i>Co-production of knowledge as a benefit to societal stakeholders.</i> • <i>FAIR data management principles for polar data collections.</i> • <i>Ensuring knowledge access and capacity building in Polar Regions.</i> • <i>Exploiting knowledge to inform decision making for the Polar Regions.</i> 	
Comments (motivate):	

Is the proposed work expected to provide an added value to the EU-PolarNet 2 project?	Choose: Yes - No
<i>EU-PolarNet 2 provides a coordination platform to co-develop strategies to advance the European Polar Research action and its contribution to the policy-making processes.</i>	
Comments (motivate):	

PART II: EXPERT EVALUATION

Note that offers that do not fully comply with the scope of the call (PART I of this evaluation file) are not eligible for funding. For those offers PART II of this evaluation file should not be completed.

Quality of the offer

Is the focus of the offer with respect to the EU-PolarNet 2 project well defined?	Choose an item.
<i>The EU-PolarNet 2 project has been implemented to improve the coordination of polar research, to identify and prioritise polar research themes of high societal relevance and to support and advice European decision makers on topics related to the Polar regions.</i>	
Comments (motivate your score):	

Are the objectives of the offer well thought out and clearly stated?	Choose an item.
Comments (motivate your score):	

Is the stake- and right holder community well targeted and involved (composition, type of involvement...)?	Choose an item.
<i>Possible stake- and right holders: researchers, local and Indigenous Arctic communities, Polar industries and businesses, non-governmental organisations, ...</i>	
Comments (motivate your score):	

Is the implementation of the service coherent with respect to its objectives: management, approaches and tools.	Choose an item.
Comments (motivate your score):	

Is the expected service impact well assessed, measured, feasible and realistic?	Choose an item.
Comments (motivate your score):	

Are dissemination activities addressing the general public/stakeholders/research community planned?	Choose an item.
Comments (motivate your score):	

Tasks, budget, timing

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adequacy of tasks and relevance of their distribution in the Action network with respect to the objectives of the offer. • Adequacy of the timing. • Fair and adequate distribution of resources. 	Choose an item.
Comments (motivate your score):	

General appreciation

--

The "qualitative evaluations" will be transferred into "numeric scores" according to the following table. For "Quality of the offer" the average of the 7 scores will be taken into account for the final numeric evaluation result on this criterion.

Insufficient information	0
Deficient	1
Weak	2
Reasonable	3
Good	4
Excellent	5

5.2 Standard Service Contract

CONTRACT FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT SERVICES

This Contract for Research Services (the “**Contract**”) is entered into force on **DD. Month YYYY** (“**Effective Date**”) between:

The Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung [Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research] (hereinafter, “**AWI**”), Bremerhaven, Germany

and

Name, Position, Affiliation/Institution (hereinafter, “Service Provider”), Address, Country

RECITALS

1. Whereas the Parties agree that such Services shall be provided to AWI by **[Service Provider]** in accordance with the terms and conditions of this Contract (as detailed hereunder) and will be governed by the technical specifications stated in the Service Offer (Annex I).
2. Whereas AWI declares, at the time of signing this Contract, that it is fully aware of how the services will be developed, in accordance with the the extent and nature of the works to be performed by **[Service Provider]** and of the risks and contingencies thereof.
3. Whereas the Parties agree to enter into this Contract for research and terms and conditions set out in this Contract.

§ 1. Subject to the Contract

1. The subject of the Contract is **[subject of Service Offer and short description of the provided Service]** according to the Offer submitted to the EU-PolarNet 2 Call for Services. This includes the submission of a report to EU-PolarNet 2 (see Annex I to Service Contract) of the work performed, a short description of the recommended research activities and a publishable summary for dissemination. It must explicitly refer to a comment on the fulfilment of the points of the work plan outlined the Offer.
2. **[Service Provider]** **[if applicable: in cooperation with [partner name]]** agree to use good scientific practice to complete the tasks defined in the EU-PolarNet 2 Call for Services Offer and shall in doing so utilise its own knowledge and experience, especially in the field concerned in this case.

The AWI may obtain information about the execution of the Contract at any time either itself or by means of reports which shall be provided promptly by the **[Service Provider]**.

3. All deliverables, materials and results provided by either Party to the other are provided "AS IS", without warranty of any kind specifically implied warranties of satisfactory quality and fitness for a particular purpose or use are excluded. Each Party specifically disclaims implied warranties of satisfactory quality and fitness for a particular purpose and any warranty against infringement of any intellectual property right of any third Party or any warranty arising out of any proposal or specification. All these warranties are hereby disclaimed. However, each Party warrants that it has the power and authority to enter into this Contract and to perform its obligations.
4. The documents and records which are to be created with the work performed shall be handed over to the AWI in electronic form no later than the date of the agreed service delivery pursuant to § 3 or after premature termination of the contract, if they have been created.
5. The Parties may periodically review any proposed changes to the tasks and examine the impact that these changes may have on the Contract, which may include schedule and costs. Either Party may request in writing that the tasks be updated with the new requirements. Both Parties before its incorporation into the Service Contract must approve this update in writing by signing an amendment to the Service Contract. Notwithstanding the foregoing, proposed changes to the tasks may not substantially differ from the tasks defined in the EU-PolarNet 2 Offer presented by the [Service Provider] and Annexed to this Service Contract.

§ 2 Execution of the Contract

1. The AWI may demand immediate changes from the [Service Provider] if it establishes that the continuity of performance of the services pursuant to the work specifications in § 1 Point 1 is not guaranteed.
2. Interruptions to execution of the contractual assignment shall be agreed between the AWI and the [Service Provider] in advance.
3. The [Service Provider] undertakes to inform the AWI about the status of the work at any time at the AWI's request.

[IF APPLICABLE:]

4. The [Institution] is a partner in the project and will collaborate with [Service Provider] to carry out the following services: [description of services performed by partner] according to the Offer submitted by [Service Provider] to the EU-PolarNet 2 Call for Services - see Annex I to Service Contract).]

§ 3 Deadline for completion

The contractual services for this Contract shall be rendered by [Date].

§ 4 Remuneration

1. A fixed price of € [amount granted] plus the statutory value added tax if applicable, shall be set for this Contract. This remuneration covers all the services rendered.
2. This remuneration also applies to work pursuant to § 2 para. 1 unless the parties come to an alternative arrangement in writing.
3. If travel is required in connection with the work to be rendered in accordance with § 1, it will be compensated with the remuneration agreed in § 4. No claim to additional remuneration exists.
4. The [Service Provider] is responsible for dealing with the tax and social security aspects of the work. The AWI shall notify the competent tax office accordingly on request.
5. The deadline for rendering the contractual services specified in § 3 is the latest possible date for completing the work and delivering the documents pursuant to § 1. For this reason, the obligation to accept the work done and to bear the costs incurred by the [Service Provider] up to that date shall cease to apply in the event of non-compliance/default. In this case, the [Service Provider] has no right to any compensation, e.g. due to lost profit.

In fact, the [Service Provider] is then obliged to repay within one month of the date specified in § 3 any advances it has already received, unless the parties have agreed in writing to continue the Contract by mutual consent.

The AWI reserves the right to claim compensation due to a breach of the fixed deadline.

§ 5 Invoicing, payment

1. Payment shall be made in two partial payments which have to be prior approved by the EU-PolarNet 2 coordinator.
2. The invoice shall be issued to the following address by 10 December each year at the latest. Invoices which are not issued to the AWI's place of business (see below) will not be accepted.

Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung
Geschäftszimmer/Gebäude E
Am Handelshafen 12
27570 Bremerhaven, Germany

Invoices must be sent in a suitable form (PDF, MS Office formats, JPG, BMP, TIF, TXT) electronically and only to the following email address:
rechnungseingang@awi.de

If they are sent to any other email address, they cannot be recognised.

3. The [Service Provider] is obliged to list the statutory value added tax on its invoice or to inform the AWI that it is exempt from VAT by including the phrase "Exemption from VAT under section 19 of the German Turnover Tax Act (UStG).

§ 6 Acceptance

1. Acceptance of the contractual performance shall be made after the fulfillment of the contractual tasks.

2. If the contractual performance is not rendered, the **[Service Provider]** shall disclose the reasons as well as all the circumstances relating to the non-performance to the AWI in writing.

§ 7 Assignment of accounts receivable

The **[Service Provider]** may only assign claims against the AWI with legally binding effect with the AWIs written consent.

§ 8 Rights of use of the work result

The AWI, the **[Service Provider]** and **[if applicable: [partner name]]** shall have non-exclusive rights to all the results of the work (in particular, copyrights, industrial property rights, right of publication, etc.). The AWI, the **[Service Provider]** and **[if applicable: [partner name]]** are entitled to produce edited and modified versions of the work and to use them in the same way as the performance.

§ 9 Disclosure of the contents of the Contract, treatment of the AWI's information and publication of the work results.

1. The AWI, the **[Service Provider]** and **[if applicable: [partner name]]** have the sole right to disclose the contents of the Contract or parts thereof.
2. Neither Party shall use Confidential Information of the other Party disclosed to it hereunder for any purpose other than in furtherance of this Contract and the activities described herein. The recipient shall not disclose, transfer, or disseminate Confidential Information of the disclosing party to any third parties except as otherwise permitted hereunder. The recipient may disclose Confidential Information of the disclosing party only to the recipient's employees and **[Service Provider]** who have a need to know such Confidential Information and who are bound in a written confidentiality agreement with provisions no less restrictive than those required by this Contract. The recipient shall maintain Confidential Information of the disclosing party with at least the same degree of care it uses to protect its own Confidential Information of a similar nature or sensitivity, but in any event, not less than reasonable care. Each party shall without undue delay advise the other party in writing of any misappropriation or misuse of Confidential Information of the other party of which the notifying party becomes aware. Recipient shall not reproduce or replicate Confidential Information in any form except as required for the purpose of this Contract. All Confidential Information (including all copies thereof) shall at all times remain the property of the disclosing party.
3. this obligation shall continue to apply for two years beyond the term of this Contract.

§ 10 Termination

1. Either Party may, at any time during the term of this Contract and upon thirty (30) days' written notice to the other, terminate this Contract. Upon termination of this Contract, the AWI will pay the pro rata payment for the services performed until the actual date of the early termination.

2. In the event of termination, the part of the performance rendered up until termination of the Contract that is reasonable and can be verified shall be billed. In the event of termination, the total remuneration must not exceed the maximum sum pursuant to § 4 of this Contract.

§ 11 Amendment of the Contract

Any changes to the subject of the Contract shall not become effective until they have been mutually approved in writing. Any changes or additions as well as the rescission of this Contract must be in writing.

§ 12 Final provision

1. The relationships between the contracting parties with regard to the subject of the Contract shall be governed exclusively by the text of this Contract and its Annexes, to the express exclusion of any general terms and conditions of business of the **[Service Provider]**. No verbal collateral agreements have been reached. Proof relating to the contents of this Contract as well as the waiver of the written form requirement must satisfy this form.
2. Should one or more contractual provisions be or become invalid, the contracting parties shall be obliged to replace the invalid provisions with other valid provisions that come so close to the invalid provisions in terms of the commercial success that it can reasonably be assumed that the contracting parties would also have concluded the Contract with this clause.
3. The place of jurisdiction for both parties is Bremerhaven.

SIGNATURES

(SERVICE PROVIDER REPRESENTATIVE)

(TITLE)

Institution

(AWI REPRESENTATIVE)

(TITLE)

Alfred Wegener Institute,
Helmholtz Centre for
Polar and Marine Research